

Notes on the Gastric Caecum of *Centrocoris variegatus* Kolenati, 1845 (Heteroptera, Coreidae): Light and Scanning Electron Microscopic Study

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ABSTRACT:In this study, the morphology and histology of the gastric caecum of *Centrocoris variegatus* were examined with light and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). *C. variegatus* is a phytophagous species that feeds on the various plants in agricultural areas and harm them. The digestive tract of *C. variegatus* is divided into three different regions: Foregut, midgut, and hindgut. The gastric caecum is located in the posterior end of the midgut. The gastric caecum of *C. variegatus* was compared to the other species belonging to Hemiptera order and other insect groups. Obtained similarities and differences in both morphological and histological features were revealed.

KEYWORDS: Gastric caecum, histology, morphology, light microscope, scanning electron microscope

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INTRODUCTION

Heteroptera is a common suborder with more than 40.000 species identified in the world, spread on all the continents except Antarctica. Researchers have identified 140 families with more than 5800 genus belonging to the ordo Heteroptera in the world (Schuh & Slater, 1995; Henry, 2009; Kiyak, 2019). It is known that the 40 families and 1.526 species belonging to the ordo Heteroptera were identified in

Turkey (Önder et al., 2006; Küçükbaşmacı & Kiyak, 2015, 2019).

Heteroptera suborder contains species with different nutritional types. Some of the species belonging to the Heteroptera suborder are zoophagous while those of others are parasitically fed. Besides, there are also phytophagous species that cause significant damages in culture areas and crops (Kiyak, 2019).

Coreidae is a family belonging to Heteroptera

suborder. The distinctive feature of Coreidae family is that individuals have a piercing-sucking mouth type. Insects with this mouth type absorb the sap of the plant and cause the plant to dry. That's why, these pests can cause a great decrease in agricultural yield. For example, some insects belonging to this family cause serious damage to hazelnuts and decrease in quality (Gameel, 2013; Dirik, 2016; Şen & Saruhan, 2016; Şimşek & Suludere, 2018; Oğuzoğlu & Avcı, 2020).

Centrocoris variegatus Kolenati, 1845 (Heteroptera, Coreidae) is a species that spreads in the Mediterranean environment, in Cyprus and Caucasus. In Turkey, *C. variegatus* is located in Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Denizli, Elazığ, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Manisa, Muğla, and Tekirdağ provinces (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Kiyak & Akar, 2010; Öncül Abacıgil et al., 2010; Kılınç, 2013; Altın, 2019).

C. variegatus is also found in both scrub and meadow areas and agricultural areas. Öncül Abacıgil et al., (2010) stated that *C. variegatus* was detected in olive groves in Edremit (Balıkesir). Besides it is found on the canola and damages the plant (Altın, 2019). One of *C. variegatus*' host plants is *Sambucus ebulus*. Moreover, this species can also cause harm in sugar beet and spinach (Lodos, 1986; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Öncül Abacıgil et al., 2010; Kılınç, 2013).

Despite the importance, as far as we know no one has studied the gastric caecum of *C. variegatus*. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to reveal the morphological and histological structure of the gastric caecum in *C. variegatus* in order to better understand the biology of this species and thus provide the necessary information to be more effective in struggle with it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Sample Preparation for Light Microscopy (LM)

Adult individuals of *C. variegatus* were collected from various agricultural areas in July-August and brought to the laboratory environment. Individuals were stunned

with ethyl acetate fumes and their internal organs were dissected. Specimens were fixed with 10% Formaldehyde. The samples were passed through rising ethyl alcohol series (70%, 80%, 90%, 96% and 100%) for dehydration process and then embedded in paraffin blocks. Sections of 6-7 microns thick taken from paraffin blocks were stained with Hematoxylin-Eosin staining for light microscopy examinations. Afterwards, they were examined with Olympus BX51 microscope and photographed.

The Sample Preparation for Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Dissected samples were fixed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde at least 24 hours, was washed with phosphate buffer. Thereafter, the samples were passed through the rising alcohol series. Specimens were waited in amyl acetate twice and were dried at the critical point drying device (Polaron, CPD 7501). The dried samples were attached to the SEM stubs with double-sided tapes and coated with gold using the Polaron SC 502 coating device. Later on, samples were examined using a JEOL JSM SEM 6060 LV at a voltage of 5 kV (Gazi University, Faculty of Science, Laboratory of Electron Microscopy, Turkey) and photographed.

RESULTS

The alimentary canal of *C. variegatus* consists of the foregut, the midgut and the hindgut (Figure 1). The midgut is divided into four regions which are called the first, second, third and fourth ventriculus (Figure 2). The last region of the midgut, the fourth ventriculus, is separated from the other parts with the pre -sence of four longitudinal rows known as gastric caeca (Figure 2).

The outer surface of the gastric caeca is surrounded by intense trachea and tracheal networks (Figure 3), and has deeply knotty structure (Figures 3, 4). The gastric caecum is connected to the digestive canal with the structure which is known as the pylorus (Figure 5). Each caecum consists of a thin monolayer cuboidal epithelium (Figures 5, 6). The nucleus of the cuboidal cells has round shape (Figure 6).

Figure 1. Overall appearance of the alimentary canal in *Centrocoris variegatus* (Stereomicroscope).

Figure 2. The regions of the midgut in *C. variegatus* (Stereomicroscope).

Figure 3. The scanning electron micrograph of the outer surface of the gastric caecum in *C. variegatus*. Tracheal network (→) (SEM).

Figure 4. The scanning electron micrograph of the outer surface of the gastric caecum in *C. variegatus* (SEM).

Figure 5. The light micrograph of the gastric caecum and the pylorus in *C. variegatus* (Light microscope, Hemotoxilen-Eosin staining, X400).

Figure 6. The light micrograph of the gastric caecum in *C. variegatus* (Light microscope, Hemotoxilen-Eosin staining, X400).

DISCUSSION

The main role of the gastric caecum is producing the digestive enzymes in Insects (Ferreira et al., 1999). Gastric caecum founding in the midgut of many insects differ among orders with regard to shape, number, size and position (Chapman, 1988). In Hemiptera order, the alimentary canal is characterized by the presence of different appendages which open into the midgut. These different appendages which called gastric caecum are found at midgut posterior end (Glasgow, 1914). These structures vary considerable in morphologically and according to degree of development in the different families in which they belong. However, gastric caeca have essentially the same histological structure (Glasgow, 1914).

The midgut of *Lygaeus trivittatus* (Hemiptera, Lygaeidae) lacks of gastric caeca as in *Sphex flavipennis* Fabricius, 1793 (Hymenoptera, Sphecidae) and *Graptostcthus scrvus* (Hemiptera, Lygaeidae) (Glasgow, 1914; Kurup, 1964; Demir & Suiçmez, 2011; Gangurde et al., 2019). The gastric caeca of *Anasa tristis* (Hemiptera, Coreidae) are arranged in two rows which are extending along the posterior end of the midgut. The morphology of this region of the midgut is seen curled and undulated. While it measures between 8 and 10 mm in the adult females, this length is between 6 to 7 mm in adult males (Steinhaus et al., 1956). Woodring and Lorenz (2007) stated that the epithelial layer of the gastric caecum also forms folds in cricket *Gryllus bimaculatus*. A different study showed us the short gastric cecacum which is located in the fifth section of the midgut *Largus californicus* (Hemiptera, Largidae), consisting of two rows of tubes (Gordon et al., 2016). The midgut of *Euschistus conspersus* (Hemiptera, Pentatomidae) has four distinct areas as first, second, third and fourth stomach. The caecal region is arranged in four rows in where called the fourth stomach. In the adult females, the caecal region is between 6.5 and 7.5 mm in length, but it varies

approximately between 5 and 6 mm in adult males (Steinhaus et al., 1956). In midgut of *Halys dentatus* (Hemiptera, Pentatomidae) which is divided into four regions, four rows of twisted gastric caecae surround the forth ventriculus (Gangurde et al., 2019).

Investigations on the different insect orders are showed that *Pylaemenes mitratus* (Basillidae) which belongs to Phasmatodea order, has two regions of midgut, which are gastric caecum and the ventriculus. It was determined that the gastric caecum which is located in the anterior midgut, is made up of finger-like smaller seven projections (Nasir & Azman, 2019).

The gastric caecum of *Aedes aegypti* (Culicidae) belongs to Diptera order, is located in the anterior midgut. Lemos et al., 2018 indicated that are it contains three parts as two laterals and one central.

In Orthoptera order, another study is indicated that *Gampsocleis gratiosa* (Orthoptera, Tettigoniidae) has two large gastric bulbous caeca attached at the anterior end of the midgut (Li et al., 2018). Similarly, *Grylloides sigillatus* (Orthoptera, Gryllidae) has two large gastric caeca in anterior region of the midgut. These are wide at the junction area to the digestive system, whereas its distal parts are narrower (Biagio et al., 2009). Besides, *Melanogryllus desertus* (Orthoptera, Gryllidae), *Rhynchosciara americana* (Diptera) and *Sitophilus granarius* (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) have two gastric caeca connected to their alimentary canals (Ferreira et al., 1981; Baker et al., 1984; Çakıcı & Ergen, 2012). On the contrary, the alimentary canal of larval blow fly *Chrysomya megacephala* (Diptera, Calliphoridae) has four gastric caeca (Boonsriwong et al., 2007). The morphology and located area of the gastric caecum of *G. bimaculatus* (Orthoptera, Gryllidae) and *Poecilimon cervus* (Orthoptera, Tettigoniidae) are similar with other discussed species in Orthoptera order in this paper (Woodring & Lorenz, 2007; Polat, 2016).

When the gastric caecum of *C. variegatus*

compared with the gastric caecum morphology of above-mentioned species belonging to different order, shows similarity in terms of the location of gastric caecum with other species in Hemiptera order. However, it differs from other Hemiptera species as the number by having four rows of tubes in the posterior midgut.

When the gastric caecum examined histologically, some differences can be observed among different orders. In some species belongs to Orthoptera order such as *Gampsocleis gratiosa* (Tettigoniidae), *G. bimaculatus* (Gryllidae), *G. sigillatus* (Gryllidae), *Mecopoda niponensi* (Mecopodidae), *Poecilimon cervus* (Tettigoniidae) epithelial folds forward to the lumen can increase the area of the gastric caeca (Li and Zheng, 2004; Woodring & Lorenz, 2007 Biagio et al., 2009; Polat, 2016, Li et al., 2018). In *C. variegatus*, the epithelium of the gastric caecum doesn't show folds forward to the lumen.

Lemos et al., (2018) shown that the gastric caeca cells of *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera, Culicidae) which have microvilli on the apical membrane, are large and slightly flattened. Additionally, the investigators expressed that the wall of the gastric caecum is surrounded with a single layer epithelium (Lemos et al., 2018). Although the gastric caecum of *C. variegatus* has similar cell layer with the gastric caecum of *A. aegypti* as histologically, the microvillus was not observed on the apical membrane of the cells. The gastric caecum has columnar cells in *M. desertus*, *Acheta domesticus* (Orthoptera, Gryllidae), *Abracris flavolineata* (Orthoptera, Acrididae), and polyhedral cells in *R. americana* (Ferreira et al., 1891; Marana et al., 1997; Rost-Roszkowska, 2008; Çakıcı & Ergen, 2012). In *Callosbruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera, Bruchidae) and *Graphosoma lienatum* (Heteroptera, Pentatomidae), the gastric caecum is lined by a monolayer cuboidal epithelium (Amutkan, 2012; Moamen and El Bakary, 2020) in a similar manner with the gastric caecum of *C. variegatus*.

Gangurde et al., (2019) indicated that presence or absence of gastric caeca in alimentary canals species of Hemiptera order has both an importance in phylogenetic and nutritional point of view.

With this study, we revealed the morphological and histological features of the gastric caecum in *C. variegatus* and compared it with those in other insect groups. We hope that the result of our study will serve as a base for the further studies.

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